

Original Research

Impact of Corporate Governance Norms on Bank Financial Performance in Bangladesh

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Abstract

The study explored the affinity between corporate governance (CG) norms and bank financial performance using data compiled from the annual reports of Dhaka Stock Exchange-listed commercial banks in Bangladesh covering a period from 2016 to 2022. Both descriptive and inferential statistics capture the effects of CG norms on the financial performance of banks. The fixed effects model (FEM) results revealed that board independence, educational qualifications of CEOs, and long-serving CEOs are positively linked with the financial performance (measured as ROA) of banks in Bangladesh but are not statistically significant. The board meeting frequency is inversely and significantly related to ROA. Banks should ensure the enactment of sound CG norms to enhance banks' financial performance and protect the shelter less tiny shareholders. The regulatory authorities must ensure compliance with CG norms and enforce penalties for non-compliance to support the banking industry's growth. The study aspires to strengthen CG norms, which go beyond the rights and duties of various stakeholders in the management of a firm. The affinity between fund providers and the bank and its compliance with legal, ethical, and environmental needs, among other things, significantly contributed to expanding our knowledge base, both in theory and in reality.

Keywords: Bangladesh, corporate governance, Dhaka Stock Exchange, firm performance.

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Introduction

In today's competitive economy, the success of any country significantly relies on the critical role of clarity, combativeness, and governance of business firms that function inside its domain (Maniruzzaman, 2023; Medvedev, 2016). Hence, sound corporate governance (CG) is essential to boost investors' trust and goodwill while ensuring accuracy, clarity, and accountability (Wahyudin & Solikhah, 2017). Gompers et al. (2003) observed that CG increases company valuation and profitability. Ararat et al. (2021) advanced that CG helps businesses through increased access to cheaper funding, improved performance, and more favorable treatment to all stakeholders. CG literature, such as Tjahjadi et al. (2021), Rudyanto & Veronica Siregar (2018), Gompers et al. (2003), and Maniruzzaman & Hossain (2019), unanimously supported the claim that sound CG reinforces business performance.

However, numerous high-performing companies misinterpret the mark due to ineffective CG (Maniruzzaman & Hossain, 2019b; Puni & Anlesinya, 2020). The lower level of growth in emerging economies is due to a need for fitting CG devices (Im & Chung, 2017). The World Bank and others have identified such countries due to their impaired ability to manage resources effectively, efficiently, and productively (Santiso, 2001). CG has emerged in contemporary research as the most pressing issue facing economically evolving countries like Bangladesh. Due to technological progress and deregulation, commercial banks have been undergoing extensive pressure to improve their services in recent years (Bos et al., 2013). Foreign banks are also entering the local markets owing to the noninterference of the economic policy, eroding local banks' monopoly position and resulting in poorer productivity and profitability. Because of the unique features of bank financial institutions and their support for Bangladesh's economy and the scarcity of such a study, it is essential to accomplish this research. Despite some recent studies by Rashid (2018), Khan et al. (2013), and (Farooque et al. (2007), there needs to be more research on the theme in emerging economies, particularly in Bangladesh. CG has become a hot topic due to its influential role in economic progress and the transition of a nation (Din et al., 2022).

In Bangladesh, embezzling thousands of crores of taka to obtain bank loans becomes a regular occurrence. Such embezzlement occasionally occurs under the guise of business and industrial financing and occasionally through outright fraud and deception. The most recent additions to this parade are the Tk 16,000 crore LC fraud from Social Islami Bank and the Tk 30,000 crore loan scam from Islami Bank by S Alam Group (Mustafa, 2023). In 2010, Yunus Badal became one of Janata Bank's biggest debtors. In just six years, Janata Bank gave him loans of Tk 5,000 crore, breaking the regulations for loan approval. Tanvir Mahmood, the leading con artist in the Sonali Bank-Hallmark fraud, stole Tk 2,731 billion. Both evolved into successful entrepreneurs, with Badal eventually coming to possess 22 businesses. These episodes cannot be referred to as extraordinary events because they are meticulously planned and supported by various institutional patronages. Instead, they must be viewed as a well-established system of capital accumulation through the theft of tax dollars (Mustafa, 2023). Furthermore, the ROA (return on assets) of private commercial banks (PCBs) in Bangladesh is getting worse over the years (see Table 1). What matters for the decreasing trend of ROA and fraudulent activities in the

banking sectors of Bangladesh is a burning question that motivates us to undertake the current inquiry.

Table 1. Profitability Ratios Measured as ROA by Types of Banks

Bank Types	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
SCBs	-0.16	0.21	-1.30	-0.61	-1.07	0.13	0.21
SBs	-2.80	-0.62	-2.77	-3.31	-3.01	-3.20	-3.31
PCBs	1.03	0.89	0.79	0.77	0.70	0.62	0.59
FCBs	2.56	2.24	2.23	2.30	2.13	1.48	2.57
Total	0.68	0.74	0.25	0.43	0.25	0.50	0.52

Source: Department of Off-site Supervision, Bangladesh Bank
 (<https://www.bb.org.bd/pub/annual/anreport/ar2022-2023/chap5.pdf>)

As such, this research looks into the link between CG and financial performance in the banking sector in Bangladesh. The study is vital for the sustainable growth of this sector, the money market, and the economy of Bangladesh. In addition to the introduction, this research is divided into five sections: the literature review, the methodology that regulates the investigation, data analysis, deliberations of the findings, and conclusions with policy recommendations.

Literature and Formulation of Hypothesis

CG received much attention from academicians, researchers, and policymakers in the last couple of decades due to its significant influence on firm performance, particularly in emerging economies where regulatory and legal enforcement is not stringent compared to developed countries. (Porta et al. (2000) opined that CG deals with how suppliers of credit get assurance that they will obtain a fair return on their investment by placing it on a platform that discloses the relationship between providers of finance and enterprises. Institutional collapse and failure at the global level due to unforeseen events prompted a fresh wave of CG concepts and views on how businesses should function (Mallin, 2016). It is evident in prior studies that the management of a corporation and its survival is linked with its leadership in place and the global competitive climate. Banks' CG is much more critical compared to other organizations (Alexander, 2006) because banks collect about ninety percent of their funds from the savers, which are repayable on demand, and the remaining amount is collected from issuing shares and other sources. So, the nature of funds and their investment procedures make banks' run opaque. A small rumor can cause bank failure if all depositors on the same day come in the bank to withdraw their deposits. Banks will be unable to honor the customers, and thus, banks will fall into trouble. Banks act as an economically vibrant sector of almost every economy (Colander et al., 2009). A resilient form of bank financial institution is a precondition for the progress of a country (JAHID et al., 2020). As such, the recent scams and scandals in the banking sectors of Bangladesh reinforce the need for well-articulated CG mechanisms and a revisit to see the effectiveness of the existing CG framework (Khan et al., 2013). This study conceptualizes the CG framework in light of agency and stakeholders' theories. Agency theory explains the conflict of interest between owners and agents, and stakeholder theory explains the relationship between managers and different stakeholders (Panda & Leepsa, 2017). Agency problem happens when managers line up their paybacks at the cost of

owners' interest (Eisenberg et al., 1998). Agents may create agency problems by making data irregularities. In that case, less or incomplete data is disclosed by the agents to the stockholders. Agency theory predicts that if there is a struggle for interest between the agents and stockholders, the importance of the shareholders is supposed to be undermined (Eisenberg et al., 1998). Sound CG are the immense need for firms in developing countries like Bangladesh for better managerial excellence and to boost the required capital.

Hypothesis Development

Board Independence

Agency theory predicts that corporate boards oversee managerial affairs to limit the self-interested behaviors of agents (Miller, 2002). For this, there should be a component of independent directors in the corporate boardroom. The main drive behind choosing sovereign members on corporate boards of publicly held corporations is to resist any misconduct of the mainstream members and enhance the worth of panels, mainly while releasing info that can defend the interests of stakeholders (Rashid & Hossain, 2022). Independent directors do not have an active or financial relationship with their firms (Belkhir, 2009) other than a position in the boardroom. The critical feature of CG is the freedom of boards as independent directors protect the interests of all stakeholders, not only the stockholders. Their participation in the board help preserve the right of shareholders. The board members should be free to watch managerial affairs (JAHID et al., 2020). Prabowo & Simpson (2011) noted that board composition indicates the representation level by independent directors as against the total number of directors. Independent directors are selected based on their skills and expertise so that they can contribute to firm value. As such, the more the ratio of sovereign directors to total directors, the higher the financial success. Both resource dependency and agency theories endorse that the existence of independent members is positively linked with economic performance. However, outside members need to control the behaviour of the CEO as they report to the CEO (Merendino & Melville, 2019; Rizzotti et al., 2017). The observed results on the connection between board composition and monetary performance are inconclusive. It is advanced that more participation of independent members is connected to improved economic achievement (Shan, 2019; Uribe-Bohorquez et al., 2018), whereas some other studies noted that a higher percentage of autonomous members are inversely connected to economic performance (Fuzi et al., 2016; Zabri et al., 2016). Some studies could not identify whether board composition substantially relates to financial achievement. Therefore, the current research proposes that:

H₁: Board freedom is positively linked with bank financial performance.

Number of Board Meetings

Board meetings serve as a vehicle to exercise the anticipated supervisory role of a board (Ntim, 2009). Conger & Kanungo (1998) noted that the frequency of board meetings leads to value expansion as long as decisions made by the corporate board are working to reduce rivalry for interest and agency cost. Vafeas (1999), on the other hand, suggested that the sum of board meetings of corporate entities is not connected to

maximizing stockholders' value since these meetings typically focus on management reports and other regular board duties rather than using the time allotted for strategy analysis and formulation. With adverse effects on performance, board meetings are also related to costs, such as the cost of decision-making time, travelling, and directors' sitting allowances (Vafeas, 1999). According to Lipton & Lorsch (1992), irregular board meetings could prevent directors from taking excess time to debate unimportant topics. The following hypothesis is formed to confirm whether the number of board meetings impacts business success.

H₂: Board meeting frequency is positively associated with corporate economic success.

CEO's Educational Qualifications

Evidence from a vast body of available literature suggests a link between the educational background of board members and corporate economic successes (Bantel & Jackson, 1989; Conger & Kanungo, 1998; Kagzi & Guha, 2018). Despite many experiential investigations on that connection, the results have been conflicting. Despite some research supporting a positive relationship, several empirical studies support an adverse link. Cheng (2008) observed a positive association between board chair education and performance in Chinese enterprises. Bantel & Jackson (1989) state that directors having higher education are more inclined to support technical advancement. Firms with senior executives who have less traditional education perform better (Conger & Kanungo, 1998). According to Bantel & Jackson (1989), highly educated directors increase the probability of making decisive moves to corporate policies. However, several studies have found a conflict between the board's educational diversity and the economic success of their firms (Hafsi & Turgut, 2013; Kagzi & Guha, 2018). Boadi & Osarfo (2019) discovered that corporate boards with more effective learning disparities would adversely impact business profitability, particularly in firms with governmental ties where the culture of selecting successful directors depends more on governance traits than academic credentials. According to Dittmann et al. (2010), bankers on corporate boards other than banking companies in Germany are linked negatively with corporate performance. This research, thus, formulates the following proposition:

H₃: CEOs' educational diversities are positively linked with bank financial performance.

CEOs' Tenure

When all other factors are alike, the long-lasting the CEO's tenure, the higher the company's performance (Simsek, 2007). This is because CEOs require the protection of their jobs to make decisions that would improve firm performance (Chen et al., 2018). CEOs make short-term, mid-term, and long-term strategic decisions (Wilkinson et al., 2006). Long-term decisions help a company significantly since the benefits compound for an extended period and assure its enduring existence. If adequate monitoring of CEOs is nonexistent, then there is a risk that they may be arrogant and extend their authority, which is known as imperial control (Luo et al., 2014). The above discussion prompted the authors to form the following hypothesis.

H₄: Long tenure of the CEO position is connected with higher corporate economic performance

Methodology

This study is quantitative since it endeavors to quantify social phenomena and analyze numerical data on the relationships between a limited numbers of attributes across a large sample. The study used the deductive research method based on the positivist paradigm.

Study Population and Sample

The study population is the DSE-listed banks in Bangladesh. As of December 31, 2022, 32 were banks listed on DSE but 30 banks were selected based on the data availability criteria. The study used yearly reports from all listed banks in Bangladesh from 2017 to 2022, resulting in a total of $(30 \times 6) = 180$ sample-year observations (Ullah et al., 2019). The yearly report serves as the primary data source for all dependent and independent variables.

Model's Specifications

To test the effects of CG devices on bank financial performance, the present study uses the following regression model:

$$Y_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1 \times ID_{it} + \beta_2 \times BM_{it} + \beta_3 \times CE_{it} + \beta_4 \times CT_{it} + \beta_j Con_{it} + \varepsilon_{it}$$

Where,

Y_{it} refers to firm performance, assessed as ROA, i.e., return on assets.

ID denotes the board freedom assessed as the sum of non-administrative members on the board.

BM refers to the sum of board meetings held in a year.

CE refers to the educational qualification of CEOs (see Table 2)

CT indicates the service tenure of CEOs

Variable Definition and Measurement

Table 2. Variable Description and Measurement

Variables		Measure
Independent Variables		
Board Independence (ID)	The proportion of outside members on the corporate board to total members.	
Board Meeting (BM)	Total number of board meetings held in a year	
CEO's educational qualifications (CE)	CEO's total academic qualifications, where the CEO earns value 1(one) for a master's degree, 1(one) for a foreign degree, 1(one) for a research degree and 1(one) for an accounting education degree.	
CEO's Tenure (CT)	CT shows the number of years of career in top executives' service in different firms. It is assessed by the natural log of CEO's total service experience.	
Dependent Variable		
Return on Assets (ROA)	The portion of operating income (EBIT) to total assets	This ratio shows how profitable a company is in relation to its entire assets $ROA = \frac{\text{Operating income}}{\text{Total assets}}$
Control Variables		
Firm Size	It is assessed by the natural log of entire assets.	
Firm Age	It indicates the firm's operating experience, which is the number of years since listing at DSE and expressed the firm age using the natural logarithm.	

Data Presentation and Analysis

This research presents descriptive statistics of the research (see Table 3). The average firm performance is .09318% under the ROA performance measure, ranging from a negative 9.97% to a positive 8.20%. The total self-governing directors on a board range from zero to eight, with a mean value of 2.2639

The mean firm size and age values are 12.1074 and 2.8289, respectively. The mean value of board meetings attended by the board members in a year is 18.1444. CEOs' academic qualifications reveal that some have only one degree while others have many degrees in different fields.

Table 3. Descriptive Statistics of the Study Variables

Variables	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	SD
ROA	180	-.0997	.0820	.009318	.0136287
ID	180	.00	8.00	2.2639	1.09688
BM	180	4	36	18.1444	6.4410
CT	180	.69	3.97	3.1972	.45232
CE	180	.25	1.00	.6014	.15090
TA	180	9.33	14.16	12.1074	.81544
LA	180	1.10	3.89	2.8290	.54707

Table 4 displays the correlation among explanatory variables. The correlation matrix shows that there is no multicollinearity problem in the data set because all values remain below 80% level (Mehedi et al., 2017). In addition, The VIF (variance inflation factor), which calculates the degree of multicollinearity in OLS regression analysis, confirms the above findings. Multicollinearity is thought to be the cut-off point at a VIF value of 10 (Gujarati, 2022).

Table 4. Correlation Matrix of the Study Variables

Variables	ID	BM	CT	CE	TA	LA	VIF
ID	1						1.630
BM	.106*	1					1.172
CT	.296**	-.009	1				2.113
CE	.019	-.048	-.117*	1			1.550
TA	.487**	.166**	.492**	.055	1		1.469
LA	-.151**	.132*	.265**	-.114*	.289**	1	1.099
**Correlation is substantial at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).							
*Correlation is substantial at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).							

Regression Results

The current study has performed regression analysis to examine the connection between the CG variables and corporate economic performance measured as ROA. Since the study has used panel data in the regression model, the pooled regression model may not effectively detect the level of influence of repressors on the regressed variable. Panel data may be confounded with some endogeneity problems. Therefore, this study has planned to use either the REM or the FEM to eliminate the impacts of endogeneity issues in the data set. The Breusch-Pagan test for heteroscedasticity has been used in this study. When we used the Breusch-Pagan test to analyze the association between ROA and other repressors, the p-value (.0125) recommended the rejection of the null hypothesis, and as such, there is no homoscedasticity in the distribution, and no two data groups have the same variance. To determine a suitable model between FEM and REM, the current study has performed Hausman test. Chi-sq. The statistic of the Hausman Test is 112.834411, and the P value is 0.020 ($p < .05$), which suggests FEM is more suitable than REM (Wichianrak et al., 2021). With regard to the explanatory power of FEM model in Tables 5, in terms of adjusted R2, the evidence clearly shows that the adjusted R2 is at moderate level for the performance equation. Comparing similar studies in the literature, the adjusted R2 is quite satisfactory (Farooque et al., 2007; Maniruzzaman et al., 2023). Durbin Watson's value confirms the model's validity (Ode-Ichakpa et al., 2020).

The FEM (see Table 5) reveals that ID (t -value=0.031484 and p -value=.9749) positively correlates with ROA, though the outcomes are not statistically significant. BM is negatively linked to ROA (t =-2.212740 and p =0.0277) and the association is significant. Furthermore, CE is positively related to ROA (t =0.606516 and p =.5446) though the tie is not statistically significant. CT is also positively related to ROA (t =.249522 and p = .8031) and the extent of relation is not significant. Besides, this research incorporates some firm level control variables in the regression model like TA and LA. The effects of TA on ROA (t =-5.533535 and p =.0000) is negative and statistically significant at 1% level but the LA has positive effects on ROA (t =1.619958 and p =.0863) and the degree of affinity is significant at 10% level.

Discussions

Most crisis-affected nations have focused on establishing and implementing sound CG practices due to the 1997–1998 Asian Financial Crisis and numerous dubious corporate failures in Europe and the USA (Detthamrong et al., 2017). As a result, businesses must cultivate a culture of awareness, openness, and accountability to build long-term value and maintain solid financial health. The research has established several theories regarding the connection between CG and corporate financial performance. There are conflicting findings about the correlation between corporate performance and CG traits, more notably board freedom, board meeting presence, CEOs' educational qualifications, and CEOs' experiences.

We plan to discuss the connection between CG mechanisms and firm performance based on the FEM. Information was gathered from the annual reports of Bangladeshi banks listed on the DSE between 2017 and 2022, six years. The agency and stakeholder theories served as the foundation for this investigation. This research aimed to explore the impact of firm-level CG structure, including board freedom, board meeting attendance, CEO education, and CEO experience, on corporate financial success as measured by ROA (An accounting-based measure). Additionally, the researchers observed the effect of company size and age on corporate financial accomplishment. Four hypotheses have been set and tested using the FEM to arrest the impacts of CG structure on financial performance.

According to the first hypothesis, the affinity between boardroom freedom and corporate success. The FEM shows a positive connection between board independence and economic achievement. However, the association is not statistically significant in the context of Bangladeshi commercial banks. These results are supported by Maniruzzaman et al. (2023), Merendino & Melville (2019), Rizzotti et al. (2017), and Rodriguez-Fernandez et al. (2014). They explained that outside directors fail to control the behavior of the CEO as they report to him/her. Despite the widespread misconception that independent external members should perform in the best interest of shareholders because of the law and that board freedom is encouraged by many international CG guidelines, the scenario in Bangladesh is different. In such a situation, these board members have become ineffective in adding value even in some advanced countries; this result is unsurprising (see Baysinger & Butler (1985); Dalton et al. (1999)). In Bangladesh, "independent" directors are usually the existing or earlier govt. Officials. They are recruited to help corporations obtain licenses or as compensation for earlier favors, claim Sobhan & Werner (2003). When they require a second opinion, boards turn to outside experts or advisors. For experts, this means that regulators must consider independent members' education, credibility, and experience.

Listed companies in Bangladesh are characterized by concentrated ownership (Maniruzzaman et al., 2023); however, achieving board independence is challenging, and the board has little responsibility in overseeing management. It is one of the reasons why board independence does not work in corporate value maximization in most Bangladeshi corporations, according to (Rashid, 2018). Next, the impression of broad freedom is not widely used in evolving markets. This concept originates, particularly in the Anglo-American context, because corporate boards in these countries are one-tier or

management boards. Both executive and non-executive directors make up this board, where the non-executive directors will provide significant assistance to the executive directors, who are responsible for the day-to-day management. Even non-executives can be given some board responsibilities.

As a result, the non-executive directors will be held to a higher standard of accountability than the supervisory board. The primary goal is to maximize shareholder wealth, and management and directors act as the shareholders' agents (maximizing returns for shareholders). There is a considerable information asymmetry between shareholders and management due to the vast number of widely dispersed owners in this traditional setting of the agency problem, rendering shareholders' influence on command, at best, insignificantly. Due to their undiversified human resource investment in a single enterprise, business managers in these countries accomplish some opportunistic behaviors. Board independence may counterbalance between the board and management (Miller et al., 2013).

In contrast to numerous countries in continental Europe, including Germany, Finland, and the Netherlands, corporate boards exist in Bangladesh under common law tradition (as opposed to civil law) (Rashid, 2018). As is most common in Anglo-American countries like the United States, United Kingdom, Canada, Australia, and New Zealand, the executive and non-executive directors collaborate in a single organizational layer without a supervisory board. Dominant family members heavily influence listed firms in Bangladesh despite similar corporate board practices in Anglo-American countries (such as one-tier boards and common law tradition). Unlike professional managers in Anglo-American nations, in emerging economies like Bangladesh, family owners are on the bank board and in management. Many listed enterprises in Bangladesh experience weak monitoring and control due to the inclusion of dominant family members on bank boards and in direction. Such family influence occasionally may adversely impact the bank. The efficacy of the Western-dominated CG structure in emerging markets has been questioned (Uddin & Choudhury, 2008). They also mentioned dominant families and close relatives might undermine the effectiveness of logical safeguards like rules and regulations for responsibility.

Table 5. Panel regression results for ROA

Variables	FEM	
	t-value	P-value
ID	0.031484	.9749
BM	-2.212740	0.0277**
CE	0.606516	.5446
CT	.249522	.8031
TA	-5.533535	.0000**
LA	1.619958	.0863
R ²	.689377	
Adj. R ²	0.637776	
F Statistics	13.35956	
Prob.	Sig.	
Durbin-Watson stat.	1.523929	
Hausman Test: Chi-sq. Statistic Prob.	112.834411 Sig	

The second hypothesis is to detect the association between the extent of the Board members' (BODs) presence in the BODs meeting and ROA. The regression results reveal that the time of members' presence in the board meeting is correlated inversely with the bank's financial performance measured as ROA (see Table 5). The above findings are similar to the outcomes of Vafeas (1999) , who noted that the meetings of the BODs are related to costs. For instance, the cost of executive time and travel expenses of board members have negative consequences on performance. However, some earlier studies do not support the results (such as Lipton & Lorsch (1992); Jensen (1993) . They noted that occasional board meetings need to allow more time for members to debate the crucial topics that need special consideration.

Furthermore, the study develops a third hypothesis to examine the effects of CEOs' educational qualifications on ROA. The results of the regression models show that CEO's academic qualifications are positively associated with ROA though the impact is statistically insignificant in FEM (see Table 5). This result signals that the CEO's educational level cannot influence the banking performance in emerging economies like Bangladesh. This study outcome is supported by some past literature (Kagzi & Guha, 2018; Hafsi & Turgut, 2013) . According to Boadi & Osarfo (2019) and Bhagat et al. (2010) , the observable features may be essential in shaping how organizations behave because it is challenging to identify and assess the unobservable variables. In Bangladesh, shareholding owners are dominant in shaping corporate behaviour. CEOs are prone to fulfil the desire of controlling directors because their appointment and renewal mainly depend on their will. Therefore, CEOs of Bangladeshi banks still need to apply their talent and skills in managing the affairs of businesses, which yields poor lending initiatives.

Consequently, non-performing loans are increasing year after year. Thus, the educational qualifications of CEOs matter little in reinforcing the performance of the Bangladeshi-listed banks in most cases. Boadi & Osarfo (2019) findings that a board with greater educational diversity will negatively influence business performance add to this argument. However, some other past studies do not support the outcome of this study (Bantel & Jackson, 1989; Conger & Kanungo, 1998; Kagzi & Guha, 2018). According to Bantel & Jackson (1989) , board members who have more excellent education are more likely to take the initiative to develop technological advances. According to (Hambrick & Mason (1984) , organizations with senior managers who have less formal education exhibit more significant performance variability. Conger & Kanungo (1998) demonstrate that the type of education (i.e., a substantial area of study) affects the firm's strategic decision models, which supports Hambrick and Mason's theory. Higher education increases a board member's likelihood of making significant changes to corporate strategy, according to Bantel & Jackson (1989). According to Bhagat et al. (2010) , the observable features may be essential in shaping how organizations behave because it is challenging to identify and assess the unobservable variables. Hambrick & Mason (1984), who contend that visible traits are regarded as a trustworthy proxy for their beliefs and knowledge base, lend more credence to this position. It may always have a significant impact on managerial behavior. The findings of (Darmadi, 2013) provide confidence in the argument that board members' educational backgrounds matter in Indonesia.

The fourth hypothesis of the study is to explore the influence of CEOs' experience on ROA. The regression outcomes (see Table 5) disclosed that the CEO's experience is

linked positively with corporate financial performance measured as ROA, but the associations are insignificant. The outcomes reveal that CEOs' experience fails to impact corporate financial performance in emerging markets. The findings are similar to Luo et al. (2014) because if good techniques for supervising CEOs are not applied, they become arrogant and try to boost their authority, a practice known as imperial control. Firm performance usually depends on CEO traits that are challenging to develop outside, such as intelligence or personality, or on information and abilities that are either not taught in schools or taught ineffectively, or taught, but also obtainable from other sources (Lindorff & Prior Jonson, 2013).

Moreover, the current study wishes to see the effects of firm characteristics on corporate financial performance. The FEM (see Table 5) shows that bank size is linked negatively with bank financial performance at a 10 percent significance level. The result reveals that big banks need to manage their financial resources profitably. These outcomes confirm that experienced banks are more capable of influencing financial performance in the context of the Bangladeshi banking industry.

Conclusion and Policy Recommendation

Conclusions

The study findings showed that most CG variables have no inspiring influence on bank profitability. The economic performance of banks is likened positively to some parameters, such as Board freedom, CEO academic qualifications, and CEO service experience, as is evident in FEM, but none of the findings are statistically significant (see Table 5). Besides, other CG variables like board members' presence in the board meetings are linked negatively with bank financial performance. The findings show that banks need suitable boards with freedom. The board should be diversified and capable of choosing the bank's emphasis on strategic choices according to the board members' credentials. A bank board should be able to control the management's opportunistic behavior and ensure an efficient internal control system. Periodic and annual financial reports are the main communication route with stockholders and other stakeholders. As such, the bank board should confirm the easy availability of annual reports.

Research Limitations

Due to data limitations, we could not study the auxiliary aspects of CG, such as insider ownership, CEO's salary, nomination and compensation committee of the board of directors, firm financial leverage, and disclosures. We also could not include non-bank financial institutions. In addition, social, economic, technological, legal, and political environmental issues are all equally significant.

Policy Recommendation and Future Research Directions

The study findings confirm that banks in Bangladesh must be in a better position to boost the money market, capital market, and economic headway. With good governance, banks would be better able to generate resources for job creation and support firms by providing credit and financial advisory services, as well as good dividends to shareholders

and boosted tax revenue for the government. Future research should explore the impacts of CG on business performance while considering the legal, social, economic, political environmental challenges, which are similar and highly essential variables.

Author Contributions

The above noted authors have contributed to prepare this manuscript. The first author develops the idea of this paper and played a major role while developing the write up of this paper. The second author contributed to design the methodology part. The third author helps in literature review and developing hypothesis and the fourth author assisted in developing the introduction part of this paper. Therefore, this is our collaborative work and has not been copied or reproduced from any sources.

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